

STUDY PROTOCOL

Effect of Obstructive Sleep Apnea-Hypopnea Syndrome Treatment on Retinal and Choroidal Parameters: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Date : January 7 , 2026

Principal Investigator: Pr. Elie MOTULSKY M.D, Ph. D^{1, 2}

Co-Investigator: Ghali BENTALEB M.D. ¹

Affiliation:

- ¹ Faculty of Medicine, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, Belgium
- ² Department of Ophthalmology, Hôpital Erasme, Hôpitaux Universitaires de Bruxelles, Université Libre de Bruxelles, 1070 Brussels, Belgium.

Email: elie.motulsky@hubruxelles.be ; ghali.bentaleb@ulb.be

Conflicts of Interest: None declared

Funding: None

Abstract

Background

Obstructive sleep apnea-hypopnea syndrome (OSAHS) affects an estimated 5 to 15 percent of the adult population worldwide and is characterized by recurrent upper airway obstruction during sleep, resulting in intermittent hypoxia, sympathetic activation, oxidative stress, and systemic endothelial dysfunction. These pathophysiological mechanisms are known to affect the retinal and choroidal vasculature, with multiple cross-sectional studies demonstrating structural thinning and microvascular impairment in affected patients. However, no meta-analysis has yet evaluated whether treatment of OSAHS reverses, stabilizes, or attenuates these retinal alterations.

Objective

This systematic review and meta-analysis aims to quantify the effect of OSAHS treatment on structural and microvascular retinal parameters measured by optical coherence tomography (OCT) and OCT angiography (OCT-A), using a within-subject pre-post interventional design. Secondary objectives include comparing treatment modalities, evaluating the influence of disease severity and follow-up duration on treatment response, and investigating the moderating effects of vascular-metabolic comorbidities.

Methods

Five electronic databases (PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase, Cochrane CENTRAL, Web of Science, and Scopus) will be searched from January 2005 to the date of the final search. Eligible studies must report paired baseline and post-treatment OCT or OCT-A measurements in adults with polysomnography-confirmed OSAHS receiving any established treatment. Random-effects meta-analyses will be performed using Hedges' *g* as the standardized effect measure. Pre-specified subgroup analyses (treatment modality, follow-up duration, disease severity) and mixed-effects meta-regression models (apnea-hypopnea index, body mass index, hypertension prevalence) will be conducted. Equivalence testing using the Two One-Sided Tests procedure will be employed to formally assess structural stability. Methodological quality will be evaluated using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale, with design-specific adaptations.

Expected results

We anticipate including 15 to 25 interventional studies. This review will provide the first pooled estimates of treatment-induced changes in retinal parameters, identify which OCT variables are most responsive to therapy, and generate evidence-based recommendations for retinal monitoring in OSAHS patients undergoing treatment.

Keywords

Obstructive sleep apnea; CPAP; upper airway surgery; retina; optical coherence tomography; OCT angiography; peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer; choroidal thickness; macular thickness; treatment effect; systematic review; meta-analysis; PRISMA

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Obstructive sleep apnea-hypopnea syndrome is a highly prevalent sleep-disordered breathing condition affecting an estimated 5 to 15 percent of adults in the general population, with rates exceeding 30 percent among individuals with obesity, hypertension, or cardiovascular disease. The disorder is characterized by repetitive episodes of partial or complete upper airway collapse during sleep, leading to cyclical patterns of hypoxia and reoxygenation that generate oxidative stress, systemic inflammation, sympathetic overactivation, and endothelial dysfunction.

The retina and choroid, by virtue of their exceptionally high metabolic demand and end-arterial vascular supply, are particularly vulnerable to the hemodynamic and hypoxic insults associated with OSAHS. Optical coherence tomography, commercially available since 2005 in its spectral-domain form, enables non-invasive, high-resolution quantification of structural parameters including peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer (pRNFL) thickness, central macular thickness (CMT), macular thickness across the Early Treatment Diabetic Retinopathy Study (ETDRS) grid sectors, macular volume, and subfoveal choroidal thickness (SFCT). OCT angiography, introduced between 2014 and 2016, further allows quantification of microvascular parameters such as vessel density in the superficial and deep capillary plexuses, foveal avascular zone geometry, and choriocapillaris perfusion.

Over the past decade, a substantial body of cross-sectional literature has accumulated, consistently demonstrating peripapillary RNFL thinning, macular thinning, and choroidal alterations in untreated OSAHS patients relative to healthy controls. Several meta-analyses have synthesized these cross-sectional findings, including those by Cheong et al. (2023), Bulloch et al. (2023), Sun et al. (2016), He et al. (2016), Wang et al. (2017), Ji et al. (2024), Wu et al. (2018), and Yu et al. (2016). Critically, all of these meta-analyses employed cross-sectional designs comparing affected patients with matched controls at a single timepoint, without evaluating whether treatment of the underlying sleep-disordered breathing modifies retinal structure or microvasculature.

1.2 Knowledge Gaps

Despite the growing interventional literature examining retinal changes following OSAHS treatment, no systematic review or meta-analysis has yet synthesized these findings. The following gaps remain unaddressed in the current evidence base. First, the pooled magnitude and direction of treatment-induced changes in retinal structural and microvascular parameters have not been quantified. Second, no formal comparison of the retinal effects of different treatment modalities (continuous positive airway pressure versus upper airway surgery versus mandibular advancement devices) has been performed. Third, the influence of follow-up duration, baseline disease severity, and vascular-metabolic comorbidities on treatment response remains unexplored at the meta-analytic level. Fourth, the question of whether treatment achieves true structural stability, rather than merely failing to detect change, has not been addressed using appropriate equivalence testing methodology.

1.3 Objectives

Primary objective

To evaluate the effect of OSAHS treatment on structural (OCT) and microvascular (OCT-A) retinal and choroidal parameters by quantifying within-subject changes from baseline to post-treatment follow-up.

Secondary objectives

The secondary objectives of this review are to compare treatment modalities (CPAP versus surgery) for their effects on retinal parameters; to determine whether the duration of follow-up (short-term versus medium-to-long-term) influences treatment response; to evaluate the moderating effect of baseline OSAHS severity on the magnitude of retinal change; to investigate whether vascular-metabolic comorbidities (hypertension, obesity) modulate the treatment effect at the study level; and to formally assess structural stability using equivalence testing methodology.

2. Methods

2.1 Study Design and Registration

This systematic review and meta-analysis of interventional studies will be conducted and reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (Page et al., BMJ 2021), the PRISMA for Protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015 recommendations (Shamseer et al., BMJ 2015), and the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions, version 6.4. The study protocol, including a pre-specified statistical analysis plan, was established prior to initiating the literature search. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic review and meta-analysis to adopt an interventional pre-post design in this field, evaluating within-subject changes in retinal and choroidal parameters following OSAHS treatment. All previously published meta-analyses examining the relationship between OSAHS and OCT parameters have employed cross-sectional designs comparing affected patients with healthy controls, without assessing treatment-induced structural changes.

2.2 Literature Search

A comprehensive literature search will be performed across five electronic databases: PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), Web of Science Core Collection, and Scopus. The search will cover the period from January 1, 2005 to the date of the final search, with no language restrictions applied at the search stage. The start date was selected to coincide with the commercial introduction of spectral-domain OCT technology (2005 to 2006), which provided the requisite axial resolution (5 to 7 micrometers) for reliable quantification of retinal and choroidal layer thicknesses.

The search strategy is structured around three conceptual blocks combined with the Boolean operator AND: (1) obstructive sleep apnea-hypopnea syndrome, (2) OCT and ocular imaging modalities, and (3) retinal, macular, and choroidal outcome parameters. No treatment-specific filter will be applied, in order to maximize search sensitivity at the identification stage; treatment relevance will instead be assessed during the screening phase, in accordance with Cochrane Handbook recommendations. Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms will be combined with free-text synonyms restricted to title and abstract fields to minimize false-positive retrieval. The full PubMed/MEDLINE search strategy is as follows:

```
("Sleep Apnea, Obstructive"[Mesh] OR "obstructive sleep apnea"[tiab] OR "obstructive sleep apnoea"[tiab] OR OSAHS[tiab] OR OSAS[tiab]) AND ("Tomography, Optical Coherence"[Mesh] OR "optical coherence tomography"[tiab] OR OCTA[tiab] OR "OCT-A"[tiab] OR "vessel density"[tiab] OR "foveal avascular zone"[tiab] OR "nerve fiber layer"[tiab] OR "choroidal thickness"[tiab] OR microvascular[tiab]) AND (retinal[tiab] OR macular[tiab] OR choroidal[tiab] OR RNFL[tiab] OR peripapillary[tiab] OR "optic nerve"[tiab] OR foveal[tiab])
```

This strategy will be adapted for each of the remaining databases using equivalent indexing terms and syntax. The complete search equations for all databases will be provided in the supplementary material. Reference lists of all included studies and of previously published systematic reviews on the topic will be manually screened to identify additional eligible reports.

Citation tracking will be performed using Google Scholar and Web of Science to capture recently published studies citing key references.

2.3 Eligibility Criteria

Eligibility criteria are defined a priori using the Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcomes, and Study design (PICOS) framework.

2.3.1 Population

The target population comprises adults aged 18 years or older with a diagnosis of OSAHS confirmed by an objective sleep study, including full polysomnography (Type I, laboratory-based), home polysomnography (Type II), respiratory polygraphy (Type III), or oximetry with airflow monitoring (Type IV) when methodological quality is acceptable. An apnea-hypopnea index of five or more events per hour is required for inclusion. All severity grades are eligible: mild (AHI 5 to 15 events per hour), moderate (AHI 15 to 30), and severe (AHI 30 or above).

2.3.2 Intervention

The intervention of interest is any established treatment for OSAHS. Eligible interventions include continuous positive airway pressure therapy (fixed CPAP, auto-titrating CPAP, or bilevel positive airway pressure, at any prescribed pressure and for any treatment duration), upper airway surgery (uvulopalatopharyngoplasty, maxillomandibular advancement, tongue base surgery, hypoglossal nerve stimulation, or other surgical techniques), mandibular advancement devices (custom-made or prefabricated), and any combination of the above.

2.3.3 Comparator

As this review focuses on within-subject treatment effects, each patient serves as his or her own control through a pre-post design, with the baseline (pre-treatment) assessment constituting the comparator. An external control group is not required for inclusion, though studies incorporating one (such as randomized controlled trials with a sham CPAP or waiting-list arm) are eligible and will be analyzed using the within-arm pre-post change to maintain consistency across all included studies.

2.3.4 Outcomes

Eligible outcomes encompass any structural parameter measured by OCT, including peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer thickness (global and by quadrant or sector), central macular thickness, macular thickness across ETDRS grid sectors (inner and outer rings), macular volume, and subfoveal choroidal thickness (including nasal and temporal measurements when available), as well as microvascular parameters assessed by OCT angiography, such as vessel density in the superficial and deep capillary plexuses, peripapillary vessel density, foveal avascular zone area and geometry, and choriocapillaris perfusion indices. Intraocular pressure and visual field indices, when reported alongside OCT parameters, will also be extracted. Studies must report outcome data at both baseline and at least one post-treatment follow-up timepoint to be eligible for quantitative pooling.

2.3.5 Study design

Eligible study designs include randomized controlled trials, prospective pre-post observational studies, prospective cohort studies with an interventional component, and case series with paired before-after analysis involving ten or more participants, provided that paired baseline and follow-up data are available. Cross-sectional comparative studies and predictive observational studies that do not report paired pre-post data may be included in the qualitative narrative synthesis but will be excluded from the quantitative pooling.

2.3.6 Exclusion criteria

Studies will be excluded if they employ a purely cross-sectional design comparing OSAHS patients with healthy controls without treatment assessment; if they are case reports or series with fewer than ten participants; if they involve animal or in vitro models; if they are narrative reviews, editorials, commentaries, or conference abstracts without complete extractable data; or if they are diagnostic or technical validation studies focused solely on OCT device performance without evaluating treatment effects. Publications before January 2005 will be excluded given the limited precision of time-domain OCT technology. When multiple publications arise from the same cohort, the most complete or the most recent report will be retained, and patient-level data will be counted only once to avoid double counting.

2.3.7 Minimum data requirements

For inclusion in the quantitative meta-analysis, studies must report, at minimum, mean and standard deviation values at baseline and at follow-up, the number of patients assessed at each timepoint, and the exact duration of post-treatment follow-up. When outcome data are presented exclusively in graphical format, numerical values will be extracted using WebPlotDigitizer software. When data are reported as medians with interquartile ranges, conversion will be performed using the method of Wan et al. (2014). If critical data are missing, corresponding authors will be contacted by standardized email, with a four-week response window.

2.4 Study Selection

Study selection will be conducted independently by two reviewers in two sequential phases using Covidence systematic review software (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia). In the first phase, titles and abstracts of all retrieved records will be screened against the predefined eligibility criteria. Records that clearly do not meet the inclusion criteria will be excluded, while those deemed potentially relevant or uncertain will be retained for full-text evaluation. In the second phase, full-text articles of the remaining records will be retrieved and independently assessed for eligibility by both reviewers using a standardized form based on the PICOS criteria described above. At each phase, disagreements will be resolved through discussion until consensus is reached or, when necessary, by consultation with a third reviewer. Inter-rater reliability will be calculated using Cohen's kappa coefficient, with a target of 0.80 or above. Reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage will be systematically documented and categorized. The study selection process will be reported in a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram.

2.5 Data Extraction

Data will be extracted independently by two reviewers using a standardized extraction form developed specifically for this review. The form will be piloted on five studies prior to full extraction to ensure consistency and completeness. Discrepancies will be resolved through discussion or by consultation with a third reviewer.

The following categories of data will be extracted from each included study: study-level characteristics (first author, year of publication, country, study design, single- or multi-center setting, follow-up duration, and loss to follow-up rate); participant demographics (sample size, mean age, sex distribution, body mass index, mean apnea-hypopnea index, OSAHS severity classification, and relevant comorbidities including hypertension and diabetes); treatment details (modality, duration, and CPAP adherence when reported); OCT and OCT-angiography technical specifications (device manufacturer and model, imaging technology, scanning protocol, and minimum accepted image quality); and outcome data (mean and standard deviation at baseline and at each available post-treatment timepoint, along with the corresponding sample size, p-value, and 95% confidence interval when reported).

For studies reporting multiple follow-up timepoints, data will be extracted at each available assessment. To avoid unit-of-analysis errors arising from the inclusion of the same participants in overlapping temporal pools, a pre-specified allocation rule will be applied: when a study contributes data at more than one timepoint that could fall within the same pooled stratum, the longest available follow-up will be assigned to the primary analysis and the shorter follow-up will be used in a sensitivity analysis. The unit of analysis will be the patient throughout, in accordance with Cochrane Handbook recommendations for ophthalmological meta-analyses; when studies report data for individual eyes, values from one randomly selected eye per patient will be used.

2.6 Quality Assessment

Methodological quality will be assessed independently by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved by consensus. The primary appraisal tool will be the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) for

cohort studies, adapted for pre-post interventional designs, scored across three domains: selection (four points), comparability (two points), and outcome (three points), yielding a maximum of nine points.

Because the included studies may encompass heterogeneous designs, the quality assessment strategy will be tailored accordingly. For any randomized controlled trial, risk of bias will be evaluated using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 (RoB 2) tool across its five standard domains (randomization process, deviations from intended interventions, missing outcome data, measurement of the outcome, and selection of the reported result). The resulting overall judgment will then be converted to a harmonized NOS-equivalent score, with randomization credited as maximum scores for the selection and comparability domains. For cross-sectional comparative studies included in the narrative synthesis only, an adapted NOS for cross-sectional designs will be applied (Herzog et al., 2013), in which follow-up items are replaced by response rate adequacy and appropriateness of exposure ascertainment, yielding an effective maximum of seven points. All scores will be reported on a unified nine-point scale to enable direct comparison across study designs, with the adaptation method noted in the corresponding table footnotes. Studies scoring seven or above out of nine will be considered high quality, those scoring four to six will be considered moderate quality, and those scoring below four will be considered low quality.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

2.7.1 Effect size calculation

Treatment effects will be quantified using the standardized mean change with change-score standardization, expressed as Hedges' *g*. For each study, the mean change will be computed as the difference between the post-treatment and pre-treatment values. The standard deviation of the change will be derived using the formula $SD_change = \sqrt{SD_pre^2 + SD_post^2 - 2 \times r \times SD_pre \times SD_post}$, where *r* denotes the pre-post correlation coefficient. Because interventional studies in this field do not report the within-subject correlation between baseline and follow-up OCT measurements, *r* will be estimated from the available data or set to a conventional default, with systematic sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of all findings to this assumption. The raw Cohen's *d* will then be corrected for small-sample bias using the Hedges correction factor *J*, yielding the final effect size Hedges' *g*. By convention, a positive standardized mean difference indicates an increase in the measured parameter following treatment, while a negative value indicates a decrease.

2.7.2 Meta-analytic model

All meta-analyses will be performed using a random-effects model, selected a priori given the anticipated clinical and methodological heterogeneity across studies arising from differences in treatment modality, follow-up duration, OSAHS severity, OCT device, and geographic setting. Between-study variance (τ^2) will be estimated using the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) method. A minimum of three studies will be required for quantitative pooling; parameters reported by fewer than three studies will be summarized narratively. Heterogeneity will be assessed using the Cochran *Q* statistic, the *I*-squared index, and the 95% prediction interval. *I*-squared values of 25, 50, and 75 percent will be interpreted as indicating low, moderate, and high heterogeneity, respectively. Leave-one-out sensitivity analyses will be performed systematically by sequentially omitting each study from the pooled estimate to evaluate the influence of individual studies on the overall result.

2.7.3 Equivalence testing

To formally assess structural stability following treatment, equivalence testing will be performed using the Two One-Sided Tests (TOST) procedure, originally developed for pharmaceutical bioequivalence studies by Schuirmann (1987) and subsequently adapted for meta-analytic applications by Lakens (2017). The rationale for this complementary analysis is that a non-significant result from a conventional two-sided test indicates only a failure to detect a difference and cannot be interpreted as evidence of stability. The equivalence margin will be set at δ equal to plus or minus 0.2, corresponding to the widely accepted Cohen threshold for a negligible standardized effect. In clinical terms, a Hedges' *g* of 0.2, translated into raw units through the average within-study standard deviations, corresponds to approximately 2 to 3 micrometers for peripapillary RNFL thickness, a value that falls below the intersession test-retest reproducibility of current spectral-domain OCT devices. Equivalence will be concluded when the 90% confidence interval of the pooled effect estimate falls entirely within the equivalence bounds.

2.7.4 Pre-specified subgroup and moderator analyses

Pre-specified subgroup analyses will be conducted to explore potential sources of heterogeneity and to evaluate clinical moderators of treatment response. Binary subgroup comparisons will be tested using the Cochran Q-between statistic, which partitions total heterogeneity into within-subgroup and between-subgroup components; a p-value below 0.05 for the between-subgroup difference will be considered indicative of a significant moderator effect. Three binary subgroup analyses are planned: temporal subgroups comparing short-term (three-month) with medium-to-long-term (six-to-twelve-month) follow-up; treatment modality subgroups comparing continuous positive airway pressure with upper airway surgery; and disease severity subgroups comparing severe OSAHS (mean study-level AHI of 30 events per hour or above) with mild-to-moderate OSAHS (mean AHI below 30).

Continuous moderator effects will be investigated using mixed-effects meta-regression models fitted with REML estimation. The moderator variables to be tested include mean study-level AHI (as a continuous measure of baseline disease severity), NOS quality score, mean body mass index, and the proportion of hypertensive patients within each study. For each meta-regression, the moderator will be centered on its sample mean to ensure that the intercept represents the predicted effect size at the average level of the moderator. The slope coefficient will be tested using a z-test, and the proportion of heterogeneity explained will be quantified as R-squared.

2.7.5 Assessment of publication bias

For outcomes with ten or more contributing studies, publication bias will be assessed by visual inspection of funnel plots and by Egger's regression test for funnel plot asymmetry, with a p-value below 0.10 considered suggestive of bias. If significant asymmetry is detected, the trim-and-fill method will be applied to estimate the number of potentially missing studies and the adjusted pooled effect. The limited statistical power of these tests when fewer than ten studies are available will be acknowledged.

2.7.6 Quality of evidence

The overall quality of evidence for each primary outcome will be evaluated using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) framework. Evidence will be rated as high, moderate, low, or very low based on five downgrading domains (risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias) and three upgrading domains (large effect size, dose-response gradient, and residual confounding favoring the null). The starting level for observational pre-post studies will be low, reflecting the inherent limitations of non-randomized designs without external controls. Summary of findings tables will be prepared for primary outcomes.

2.7.7 Software

All statistical analyses will be performed using RevMan (version 5.4; The Cochrane Collaboration) and R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria), with the metafor package for random-effects meta-analyses and meta-regressions and the TOSTER package for equivalence

testing. Forest plots will be generated in the RevMan format. All analyses will be independently verified in Stata (StataCorp, College Station, TX) to ensure computational reproducibility.

3. Expected Outcomes and Dissemination

3.1 Expected Results

Based on preliminary scoping searches, we anticipate including 15 to 25 interventional studies encompassing approximately 600 to 800 participants. The meta-analysis is expected to provide the first pooled estimates of treatment-induced changes across multiple retinal and choroidal parameters, to determine whether treatment achieves formal equivalence (structural stability) as assessed by the TOST procedure, and to identify which OCT parameters are most and least responsive to therapy. Subgroup and meta-regression analyses are expected to clarify whether treatment modality, follow-up duration, baseline disease severity, and vascular-metabolic comorbidities influence the magnitude of retinal change.

3.2 Clinical and Research Implications

This systematic review and meta-analysis will be the first to synthesize evidence on the treatment effect of OSAHS interventions on retinal parameters using a within-subject interventional design. The findings are expected to inform clinical practice by establishing whether OCT monitoring is warranted in OSAHS patients undergoing treatment, to guide treatment decisions by providing comparative data on the retinal effects of different therapeutic modalities, to support the development of clinical guidelines for retinal screening and follow-up in OSAHS, and to identify knowledge gaps and priorities for future prospective studies and randomized controlled trials.

3.3 Dissemination Plan

Results will be disseminated through publication in a peer-reviewed ophthalmology or sleep medicine journal, presentation at relevant scientific conferences, and deposit of the full protocol, dataset, and analytical code in an open-access repository. A completed PRISMA 2020 checklist will accompany the final manuscript.

3.4 Amendments

Any amendments to this protocol will be documented with the date of the amendment, a description of the change, and a rationale for the modification. All amendments will be reported in the final published systematic review.

References

1. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. 2021;372:n71.
2. Shamseer L, Moher D, Clarke M, et al. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ*. 2015;350:g7647.
3. Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, et al. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*, version 6.4. Cochrane, 2023. Available from: www.training.cochrane.org/handbook.
4. Sterne JAC, Savovic J, Page MJ, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*. 2019;366:l4898.
5. Sterne JA, Hernan MA, Reeves BC, et al. ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. *BMJ*. 2016;355:i4919.
6. Wells GA, Shea B, O'Connell D, et al. *The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) for assessing the quality of nonrandomised studies in meta-analyses*. Ottawa: Ottawa Hospital Research Institute, 2014.
7. Herzog R, Alvarez-Pasquin MJ, Diaz C, et al. Are healthcare workers' intentions to vaccinate related to their knowledge, beliefs and attitudes? A systematic review. *BMC Public Health*. 2013;13:154.
8. Borenstein M, Hedges LV, Higgins JPT, Rothstein HR. *Introduction to Meta-Analysis*. Chichester: John Wiley and Sons, 2009.
9. Schuirmann DJ. A comparison of the two one-sided tests procedure and the power approach for assessing the equivalence of average bioavailability. *J Pharmacokinet Biopharm*. 1987;15(6):657-680.
10. Lakens D. Equivalence tests: a practical primer for t tests, correlations, and meta-analyses. *Soc Psychol Personal Sci*. 2017;8(4):355-362.
11. Cohen J. *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. 2nd ed. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 1988.
12. Wan X, Wang W, Liu J, Tong T. Estimating the sample mean and standard deviation from the sample size, median, range and/or interquartile range. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2014;14:135.
13. Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Vist GE, et al. GRADE: an emerging consensus on rating quality of evidence and strength of recommendations. *BMJ*. 2008;336(7650):924-926.
14. Cheong AJY, Wang SKX, Woon CY, et al. Obstructive sleep apnoea and glaucoma: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eye (Lond)*. 2023;37(15):3065-3083.
15. Wang W, He M, Huang W. Changes of retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Curr Eye Res*. 2017;42(5):796-802.
16. Sun MH, Lee CY, Liao YJ, Wei LC. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in patients with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome: a meta-analysis. *Medicine*. 2016;95(33):e4499.

- 17.** He M, Wang W, Huang W. Choroidal thickness changes in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sleep Breath.* 2016;20(1):369-378.
- 18.** Yu JG, Mei ZM, Ye T, et al. Changes in retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in obstructive sleep apnea/hypopnea syndrome: a meta-analysis. *Ophthalmic Res.* 2016;56(2):57-67.
- 19.** Ji K, Yang Y, Ye G. Meta-analysis: characteristics of retinal vasculature in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome humans. *Biomed Res Int.* 2024;2024:5584547.
- 20.** Wu X, Liu H. Obstructive sleep apnea/hypopnea syndrome increases glaucoma risk: evidence from a meta-analysis. *Int J Clin Exp Med.* 2015;8(1):297-303.
- 21.** Bulloch G, Seth I, Zhu Z, et al. Ocular manifestations of obstructive sleep apnea: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol.* 2023;261(9):2681-2694.